

STRATEGIES FOR IMPROVING INDUSTRY QUALITY THROUGH STATISTICAL TOOLS FOR DOE

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Abstract

Today, statistical techniques have become an important tool in the development and production of new innovative products of high quality and advanced functional capabilities. They are successfully used in solving problems in various industrial spheres, in the quality management of products and to increase the efficiency of production processes, which leads to cost savings and improved competitiveness of companies in the face of strong global competition. Although they offer rich opportunities for effective problem solving of different nature, there are a number of challenges to the full adoption and application of statistical techniques by the engineering community and industry. The main barriers identified in a number of studies that severely limit the application of statistical techniques are the lack of sufficiently well-trained specialists in the field, as well as the lack of a universal methodology to simplify use in practice.

The Design of Experiments (DoE) is a precise approach that empowers scientists and engineers to explore the correlation between various input variables, also known as factors, and crucial output variables or responses.

This article presents the best practices in the training of engineering students to overcome the existing barriers and limitations regarding the wider application of statistical methods such as experiment planning by industry. For this purpose, a specialized module "DoE Training" has been developed to the training course "Quality and Reliability of Electronic Equipment" which is mandatory for engineering students of the Faculty of Physics and Technology of Plovdiv University. The module is fully focused on the practical application of DoE in experimental work to achieve optimal results in the implementation of an engineering project. In this module, the students discover the advantages of designed experiments over trial and error and the one-factor-at-a-time methods, as they provide a deeper comprehension of cause-and-effect relationships and interactions among factors. They are introduced to various types of designs, they are provided with DOE guidelines and are acquainted with best practices that greatly contribute to their success in conducting experiments.

For the better assimilation of the learning material, strategies for analysing problems have been proposed through an appropriate systematic approach, which helps to implement all the necessary steps and the selection of the right statistical tools for planning the experiment (DoE). This enables students to explore and analyse complex causal relationships in the design of electronic products and to perform optimization of important qualitative and quantitative parameters.

The proposed learning approach in the developed module has been assessed through a survey made among students after completing the course at the end of the semester. The survey shows that students consider what they have learned in the module as very useful in solving practical engineering problems, despite the challenges associated with learning the many statistical tools needed to perform the analyses.

Keywords: Design of experiments, engineering education, quality characteristics

1 INTRODUCTION

The experimentation process has become a key activity in the industrial sphere to ensure high quality, improve efficiency and reduce costs in the production of goods and services. Experimentation can be applied both to improve the functionality or efficiency of an existing product or process, and to the development and production of entirely new products, processes or services [Krishnaiah, Shahabudeen, 2012, p. 22].

Experimentation is part of the research activity of any manufacturing company, which must have enough trained engineers to qualify and analyze quality problems and quickly find a solution in order to remain competitive on the market.

In industrial production, in solving quality problems, experiments are performed [Antony, 2014, p. 13], [Phadke, 1989] with the following objectives:

- Defining behaviour, managing variations and identifying opportunities to optimise an existing product or process;
- Research and analysis of design parameters to identify optimal settings in which quality and reliability remain stable under different external conditions;
- Verification of the results obtained.

Usually, in carrying out these operations, a lot of data is generated in the experimentation process to quantify the results. For the processing of these data, appropriate statistical means are needed to improve the efficiency and reduce the time to conduct the necessary research and analysis for decision-making until the completion of the project.

To analyse data and identify complex interactions of input variables on output quality characteristics, scientists and engineers use statistical tools such as Design of Experiment (DoE) more effectively. DoE has a rich set of statistical tools to obtain valid and objective assessments with a minimum number of experiments conducted to obtain the desired results [Krishnaiah, Shahabudeen, 2012, p. 24].

The rich capabilities of DoE make it possible to effectively solve problems of different nature of science and technology. There are a number of examples of the successful implementation of DoE in the industry, yet there are problems that prevent companies and the engineering community from adopting DoE more widely [Tanco, M., Viles, E., Ilzarbe, L., Álvarez, M. J., 2007].

Some of the main reasons that negatively affect the spread of DoE in the industry are [Antony, 2014, p. 55], [Tanco, M., Viles, E., Ilzarbe, L., Álvarez, M. J., 2007]:

- First of all, the limited training of specialists in this field;
- The very theoretical teaching of this discipline;
- Misunderstanding of the competitive advantages that provide the methods of DoE in problem solving;
- The lack of a universal methodology to facilitate use in practice.

To address these challenges and overcome existing limitations, adequate training in this discipline should be offered in the engineering faculties of universities to fill the lack of specialists in the field. Training should offer good feedback between the theoretical development of DoE methods and their particular application in practice. In the process of training engineers in the field of DoE, special attention should be paid to working with statistical tools to correctly analyse and interpret results and make decisions.

This article presents a systematic approach to training engineering students to overcome the limitations related to the application of statistical methods for planning the experiment by industry in quality improvement projects. For this purpose, a specialized training module "DoE Training" has been developed entirely focused on the practical application of DoE in experimental work. This module is integrated into the compulsory discipline "Quality and reliability of electronic equipment". In this module, students learn about the most popular strategies in the industry such as Six Sigma and Design for Six Sigma (DFSS) and their application to solve problems in various projects related to quality assurance of electronic devices and systems. In order to better understand and master the learning material, a methodology has been developed with the mandatory steps in the implementation of a project and how to choose the optimal statistical tool for research and analysis of project factors and obtaining objective assessments to achieve the goal. In this way, students will be able to develop the necessary engineering and statistical competencies to solve practical engineering problems and will be prepared for the high standards of the modern electronics

industry.

The proposed approach is assessed after completing the course at the end of the semester through a survey made with 3 groups of students from different engineering specialties. The study shows that students highly appreciate the knowledge they have gained in the studied module and find it useful in solving practical engineering problems in the field of design and optimization of electronic systems.

2 METHODOLOGY

In order to meet the educational needs of engineering students of the Faculty of Physics and Technology of Plovdiv University who study the discipline "Quality and reliability of electronic equipment" and to develop their competencies in the field of statistical methods for designing experiments, an additional training module "DoE Training" has been developed.

The module "DoE Training" is focused on the application of statistical methods in projects of engineering practice and ensuring the quality and reliability of electronic equipment. The curriculum is organized so that students can understand the basic ideas for proper planning of experiments, which includes a detailed description of all activities from the beginning of a project to its completion.

After completing the course, the trainers set themselves the goal that the students have learned:

- The basic principles of design of experiment methods;
- How to choose the quality characteristics when conducting experiments;
- How to determine the range of settings in an experiment;
- How to identify key interactions or causal relationships;
- How to choose the appropriate experimental design in their projects;
- What is the role of DoE in the quality improvement initiatives Six Sigma and Design for Six Sigma (DFSS);
- What are DMAIC and DMADV procedures and their alternatives.

To achieve high educational goals and promote the benefits of the practical use of DoE in the developed training module "DoE Training" special attention is paid to business strategies to increase quality and reduce costs in the industrial sphere such as Six Sigma and Design for Six Sigma (DFSS).

Within the DoE training course, the Design for Six Sigma (DFSS) concept was demonstrated to students in a project for radiator design and optimization which is designed for a powerful LED luminaire. The aim of the design was the temperature of the luminaire LED not to exceed 600C at an ambient temperature of 250C.

In the process of project implementation, the students followed the methodology DIDOV (Design, Identify, Design, Optimize, Verify) on which DFSS is based. The DIDOV methodology focuses on the effective and reliable design of products and fits very well with the assignment in the project because the students got a real idea of how the high-quality assurance standards in the industry are met.

Figure 1 shows the related activities at each step in the DIDOV methodology [Luiten, 2011].

In the first step, "Define", students have to define the objectives of the project and make a plan to achieve the goals. This step starts with a preliminary online survey.

In the "Identify" step the user needs have to be identified and the technical parameters for forming a heat sink specification are to be determined.

In the "Design" step, a conceptual design of the chosen design solution is made, which serves to study the main thermal effects and evaluate the thermal behaviour. Then the students proceed to the creation of a CFD (Computational fluid dynamics) model, which serves to build a transfer function (it makes the connection between the parameters of the structure and their reflection on the cooling capacity of the radiator).

In the "Optimize" step, students focus on finding the optimal settings of design parameters. In this step, different statistical tools are used to find the best settings of the structure.

In the "Verify" step, students make a final check of the optimized design by conducting thermographic measurements with a prototype of the radiator structure.

Fig. 1. Activities at each step in the DIDOV methodology

3 RESULTS

The project was attended by students from three engineering specialties in the second semester of the academic year 2022-2023. In order to achieve high educational goals and successfully complete the project, students were organized to work in a team. Each team member had a clear role and responsibilities.

During the execution of the project, strong feedback was maintained between the students and the trainer in the implementation of the activities at each step in the DIDOV methodology and other issues that arose during the execution of the project.

To solve the problems related to the design and analysis of the thermal behaviour of the radiator structure, the students created a heat model using the CFD software Flotherm.

Figure 2 shows a heat model of the heat sink design for the study of thermal behaviour.

Fig. 2. Simulation results to study the thermal behaviour of the conceptual model of heat sink

The students had to deal with a number of challenges because the dimensions of the radiator were limited by the size of the luminaire.

To optimize the design of the radiator, the students used the following parameters – the number of ribs, the diameter and their height. In the optimization of the design parameters, the students used DoE analyses.

In the DoE analyses, students used a full factorial experiment for the three design factors at two levels.

Table 1 shows the possible experiments with the different design parameters of the heat sink.

Table 1. Possible experiments with the design parameters

Nº	Rib height (mm)	Rib diameter (mm)	Number of ribs
1.	20	3	24
2.	20	3	42
3.	20	4	24
4.	20	4	42
5.	40	3	24
6.	40	3	42
7.	40	4	24
8.	40	4	42

Figure 3 shows the influence factor of each parameter and combination of radiator parameters and its influence on the temperature of the luminaire LED.

Fig. 3. Graphical representation of the influence factor of design parameters on the temperature of the luminaire

The analyses performed show that the radiator with optimum design parameters has a rib height of 20 mm, a rib diameter of 2 mm and 24 ribs.

To verify the results of thermal design and simulations, the students performed thermographic measurements on a prototype of the lighting body in the specialized laboratory under the discipline "Quality and reliability of electronic equipment".

In Fig. 4 a thermogram of the luminaire is shown.

Fig. 4. Thermogram showing the maximum temperature of the luminaire

The results obtained show that the students coped with the task assigned to them and had gained enough experience to work, both with statistical tools for planning experiments and with specialized measuring equipment.

Figure 5 shows results of a survey on student satisfaction with their DoE training.

Fig. 5. Telecommunication and Information systems - TIS, Eco-energy Engineering – EET, Information and Computer Engineering – ICE

The survey was conducted at the end of the semester after the completion of the DoE training with students from three undergraduate programs in engineering studying the discipline "Quality and reliability of electronic equipment".

The survey included 10 questions for students to assess their satisfaction with the training. In the survey, each question is scored with points from 1 to 10. The maximum number of points students can score is 100. Scores above 80 points indicate sufficient satisfaction and below 60 points indicate low satisfaction.

The results of the survey show that students consider what they have learned in the module to be very useful in solving practical engineering problems, despite the challenges involved in learning the many statistical tools that are needed to perform the analyses.

4 CONCLUSION

This article presents a systematic approach to training engineering students to overcome the limitations related to the application of statistical methods for designing the experiment in industry. For this purpose, a specialized training module "DoE Training" was developed focused on the practical application of DoE in

engineering practice.

To achieve high educational goals in DoE training, attention was paid to the application of the Design for Six Sigma industrial strategy to solve problems in a project for the design and optimization of a radiator designed for a powerful luminaire.

The methodology applied in the implementation of the project allow students to acquire the necessary technical and statistical competencies to solve problems in engineering practice and easy adaptation to the future professional realization in industry.

During the training, the students upgraded their knowledge and skills and learned:

- How to plan experimental activities;
- How to choose the appropriate design to effectively determine qualitative and quantitative factors;
- How to be able to decide on the range of settings in an experiment;
- How to choose appropriate statistical tools for more effective planning and analysis of data to obtain objective estimates;
- How to work in a team.

The applied approach was evaluated with a survey made with students from three engineering specialties. The results of the survey show that the applied approach is useful in solving practical engineering problems in the field of design and optimization of electronic systems.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work is supported by National Program "Young Scientists and Postdoctoral Students" at the Ministry of Education and Science, Bulgaria.

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